

An Empirical Study of Enterprise Development Strategy on Business Performance in China

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Abstract

Based on the existing research at home and abroad, the research on the development strategy of auto parts enterprises is still less, and the research has not reached the mature stage. Therefore, taking the parts enterprises in Jiangsu Province as the research object, this paper studies the development strategy of auto parts enterprises from both theoretical and empirical aspects. The research samples are mainly represented by the auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu Province, which focuses on foreign parts companies in China. The selected research content is in addition to the questionnaire, for short-term and long-term strategy and planning, relevant research needs to be based on a long-time span. At the same time, the upgrading of the business model of the vehicle industry has also promoted the innovation of the traditional business model of the auto parts industry. In order to adapt to the current environment of economic globalization, auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu province need to constantly reform and innovate and optimize the development strategic model to improve their competitiveness, so as to better cope with the fierce external changes and seek future development. According to the conclusions, suggestions are put forward, including: at the enterprise level, we should improve the ability of technological innovation and improve the layout of enterprise resources; At the industry level, we should adapt to the pressure of market competition and strengthen the relationship with stakeholders; At the policy level, the government should create a good policy environment for auto parts manufacturing enterprises through financing channels and conditions, service contents of relevant functional departments and industry access policies.

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INTRODUCTION

Research Background

China Industry Information Network (2017) pointed out that the automobile industry is one of the largest and most important industries in the world. As the global economy increasingly diversified and complicated environment, the industry as large, involving the field of civilian consumer goods, has become the world's various industries with large scale industry, at the same time, the car industry in the process of production, but also has high production management requirements, technical requirements for comprehensive, industrial chain coverage, as well as the huge capital investment characteristics, Become an important benchmark to judge the level of development of a country's manufacturing industry. In a sense, the development level and strength of the automobile industry reflect the comprehensive national strength and competitiveness of a country. With the deepening of global economic integration and industrial division of labor, China's position in the global automobile market pattern is also increasing. Due to the rapid growth of automobile demand in The Chinese market, international automobile giants and local vehicle enterprises have increased production capacity investment in the Chinese automobile market. In 2016, China both produced and sold more than 28 million automobiles (data source: China Association of Automobile Manufacturers), ranking first in the world for many consecutive years. China's automobile industry is still the world's most potential market in the future because of its low per capita car ownership and large potential demand. With the vigorous development of China's auto industry, in recent years, China's auto industry has exceeded the United States, Japan and Germany and other traditional auto industry powers, accounting for one-third of the global market, the scale of China's auto industry has become a veritable big country of automobile production and consumption, occupy an important position in the world. As we all know, the vehicle is composed of many different types of parts, through assembly, according to statistics, the cost of auto parts accounted for 60% to 80% of the cost of the vehicle, at the same time, the auto parts industry, but also has a variety of products, large added value, strong professional, high technical requirements, wide industrial correlation and other characteristics. Auto parts industry plays an extremely important role in the development of the entire auto industry, and becomes the main carrier of core technology in the process of vehicle production. With the rapid development of the auto industry, the volume of the national economy occupied by auto parts enterprises is also increasing. Up to now, the annual sales volume of China's auto parts production industry has exceeded 4 trillion yuan, with an annual compound growth rate of more than 10%, and the foreign export volume has remained stable at more than 0.3 trillion yuan. China's auto parts industry has become an important part of the global auto parts industry. In 2019, 8 Chinese enterprises were selected into the list of "Top 100 Global Auto parts Suppliers", especially in auto glass, interior and exterior decoration, tires and wheels and other parts segments, China has gradually emerged a number of internationally competitive local enterprises. Face the continuous development of science and technology and the constantly changing consumer demand, the auto parts industry in China is also actively, in the field of new energy vehicles, developed by our country high specific energy, high security power battery efficiency, integrated electric motor control system, key parts such as heat pump air conditioning performance has achieved the international leading; In the field of auto driving, millimeter wave radar, machine vision and system algorithms developed in China have been independently developed and tested on vehicles. Although the auto parts industry

development of our country has made some achievements, but the whole industry chain from auto parts dimension, auto parts industry in China still lag behind the development of automobile industry, spare parts imported in great quantities, can neither guarantee products supply in time also make the vehicle cost is relatively high, in the global automotive industry competition at a disadvantage. How to realize the development of auto parts enterprises in product structure, technology iteration and market competition, and realize the breakthrough of generic products and key technologies are becoming the key to restrict the development of China's auto parts industry. Therefore, with the continuous updating and iteration of the automobile industry, it has become an inevitable trend to innovate and develop automobile parts enterprises, master the core technology of products and create local brands. As to be an important base of China's automobile industry, Jiangsu province has many famous automobile brands such as Changan, Dongfeng Yueda kia, and the automobile industry has gradually become an important pillar industry in Jiangsu Province. With the international competition, jiangsu auto industry chain is gradually reorganizing the industry chain and optimizing the allocation of resources. The upgrade of the whole vehicle industry has driven the great development of the auto parts industry. At the same time, the upgrade of the business model of the vehicle industry also plays a role in promoting the innovation of the traditional business model of the auto parts industry. In order to adapt to the current environment of economic globalization, jiangsu auto parts enterprises need to continue to reform and innovation, optimize the development strategy mode, to improve their competitiveness, in order to better cope with the drastic changes outside, and seek future development.

Problem Statement

Since 2017, with rapid development of automobile industry in China has gradually in the past, the industry growth is slowing, the Chinese early implement the national strategy in technology with market will face major changes (figure 1), its development made in China, development of autonomous technology industry, in this context, China's auto parts enterprises in the new environment, How to find a suitable way for their survival and development is a problem that auto parts enterprises must think about. In "The Future of The Automotive Value Chain, Supplier Industry Outlook 2025", it is mentioned that the 100-year history of the automobile Industry is facing a disruptive change. Because the market rules are always survival of the fittest, if the auto parts enterprises can not adapt to the changes in the market environment, but choose to stand still, the enterprise will be in a dangerous situation in the competition. The continuous development of the automobile industry and the emergence of various technological innovation models make the current vehicle and related industries in the future development are full of opportunities and challenges. The development of foreign auto parts companies in China may face a lot of difficulties due to the change of internal and external environment. At present, the global auto parts industry continues to expand with the prosperity of the auto market. In the 2019 World Top 500 list, auto parts giants occupy more than 10 shares, which shows that auto parts enterprises play an important role in the entire economic development. At present, due to the influence of various factors, the sales volume in China's automobile market is declining, especially with the emergence of the epidemic worldwide, which will also have a certain impact on the automobile industry. Corporate

strategic choice is the driving result of formal and informal constraints in the institutional framework faced by the firm.

Figure 1 Changing trend of automobile sales

In the future development and reform, auto parts enterprises, especially foreign auto parts companies in China, how to break through the siege is a problem that needs to be considered. The auto parts industry is the foundation of the development of the auto industry, and also an important driving force to promote and support the vigorous development of the whole industry. As an important production base of auto parts in China, Jiangsu province's main business income of auto parts accounted for about 13.5% of the national total in 2019, ranking first in the output of auto parts in China. There are more than 2,000 large-scale auto parts manufacturers in The province, mainly in Jiangsu, Yangzhou and Wuxi. Although Jiangsu province, as the champion province in the output of auto parts in China, has a good industrial base, superior geographical characteristics and abundant labor resources, compared with guangdong, Zhejiang and other economically developed provinces, its auto parts industry still has many structural problems. On the one hand, 90% of auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu province are small-scale enterprises, whose organizational structure is disorganized, industrial chain duplication is serious, overall development level is low, profitability is weak, enterprise research and development is insufficient, and core competitive technology is lacking, leading to the production of auto parts products at the low end of the whole value chain; On the other hand, most enterprises in Jiangsu province have not entered the international and domestic auto parts supporting system, and the degree of systematization, standardization and universality of parts products is low, and the ability to control the supporting system of the whole parts industry is insufficient. The development of auto parts industry in Jiangsu province lags behind, which seriously affects the development of auto industry in jiangsu province and the improvement of independent innovation ability, and is not conducive to the long-term sustainable development of the industry.

Research Objectives

Through the research on the issues raised in this paper, the author expects to achieve the following research objectives. Based on the theoretical analysis and exploration of the decision-making factors of auto parts enterprises, the theoretical model of the development strategy selection of auto parts enterprises is constructed, and the corresponding research hypotheses

are put forward. Through the study of cooperative and forward-looking development strategies of auto parts enterprises, and through confirmatory factor analysis, the long-term strategy of auto parts is further studied. AMOS software is used to compare and analyze the short-term and long-term effects of auto parts enterprises in the development process, so as to complete the consideration of the enterprise's future development plan.

Research Significance

Since 2009, China's auto sales exceeded the United States for the first time, China's vehicle production and sales in the world for many years. Although the production and sales volume is so large, China's vehicle production technology innovation and parts industry development and developed countries still have a big gap. In this context, taking Jiangsu province as the research sample, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to systematically study the strategic development of the auto parts industry, explore the innovative development path of the auto parts industry, and improve the development strategy of China's auto parts industry. The development of economic globalization has further promoted the international industrial transfer, and China has changed from a low-end subsidiary global manufacturing base to a dominant global creation base. The characteristics of industrial transfer in the world today are that the capital-intensive heavy and chemical industries, labor-intensive processes and non-core technology sectors in the high-tech industries in developed countries will accelerate the transfer to developing countries. It is of great significance to grasp the strategic opportunity of global auto parts industry development and make use of the opportunity of global auto parts industry transferring to developing countries to obtain the breakthrough development of auto parts enterprises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategic Management

Strategy, generally refers to the major, with the overall, regular planning. It was originally a category of military science, and then gradually expanded to politics, economy, science and technology, culture and other fields. Strategic management refers to the art of making decisions and management on the overall and long-term development direction, objectives, tasks and policies, as well as resource allocation of an enterprise or organization in a certain period. It includes a series of judgments made by the company on the uncertainties when the company achieves specific goals, and the company formulates strategies on the basis of environmental testing activities. Strategic management can be understood in a broad sense and a narrow sense. Strategic management in a broad sense refers to the use of strategy to manage the entire enterprise. Ansoff is the main representative of this theory, he took the lead in putting forward the concept of corporate strategy, the concept of strategic management, the system theory of strategic planning, the concept of enterprise competitive advantage, contingency theory. In his opinion, the strategic management of an enterprise refers to a series of operation and management businesses formed by combining daily business decisions with long-term planning decisions. In the narrow sense, strategic management refers to the formulation, implementation, control and correction of strategic management, represented by Steiner. He believes that enterprise strategic management is a dynamic process in which enterprise mission is determined, enterprise objectives are determined according to external environment and internal operation elements, and the correct implementation of objectives is

ensured and enterprise mission is finally realized. With Fayol, Chester Barnard, Andrews, Michael Porter and the school of Core Competence as the mainstream, strategic management has formed four important theoretical schools. The content of the specific theoretical schools is summarized as follows:

1. Fayol's management theory. The five elements of management activities proposed by Fayol are his most important contributions. These five elements are actually the five functions of management, and form a complete management process: planning, that is, predicting the future and making action plans; Organization, namely, the establishment of the structure of the enterprise in terms of material and human resources, the task of management lies in the establishment of an organization, so that it can carry out its basic activities in the most effective way; Command, is to make the organization give full play to its role, so that enterprise personnel to make the greatest contribution; Coordination is to unite enterprise personnel, so that all activities and efforts in the enterprise are unified and harmonious; Control is to test whether everything that happens in an enterprise is consistent with the plan, instructions and principles formulated. Its purpose is to discover mistakes, correct mistakes and prevent repeated mistakes. Research on enterprise strategic management in the early 1990s, the main research topic is basically the enterprise competitive relationship and competitive advantage to carry out. However, in the late 1990s, especially in the 21st century, with the acceleration of economic globalization, enterprises are faced with increasingly complex market competition and external environment, which leads to enterprises in the process of operation, once the relevant strategy formulation problems, will be likely to face a fatal blow. For the competition among enterprises, it is no longer a single competition, but a competition of enterprise management philosophy and development mode, that is, the competition of enterprise strategic management. Therefore, many researchers have done a lot of research on how to improve the competitiveness of enterprises and do a good job in enterprise development strategy planning.

Enterprise Development Strategy

Enterprise development strategy is a long-term development goal and strategic plan formulated and implemented by an enterprise on the basis of comprehensive analysis and scientific prediction of the current situation and future trend. It is one of the types of enterprise strategy. Enterprise development strategy is a general term for all kinds of enterprise strategies, including competitive strategy, marketing strategy, brand strategy, financing strategy, investment strategy, technology development strategy, talent development strategy, resource development strategy and so on. However, there are differences between the enterprise development strategy and the above strategies. The enterprise development strategy is about the strategy of enterprise development, and it is a strategy for the overall, long-term and fundamental problems in enterprise development. In brief, enterprise development strategy is the overall planning of enterprise development goals, ways and means to achieve goals according to the external environment and internal resources and capabilities, in order to seek enterprise survival and long-term stable development, to continuously obtain new competitive advantages, and to continuously improve the core competitiveness of the enterprise. Through reviewing Chinese and foreign literature, the author sorts out the relevant researches of domestic and foreign scholars on enterprise development strategy. In the 1960s, Igor Ansoff (1965) published the book *Corporate Strategy*. He was regarded as the originator

of strategic management. Besides proposing systematic strategic management theory, he also listed a series of action lists and methods. The company managers can use relevant methods to conveniently apply strategic theory to the operation management of the company, forming the basic theoretical framework of strategic management research, which is regarded as the beginning of systematic strategic theory research. In the 1980s, Wernerfelt (1984) argued in the "Resource-based Theory of enterprises" that an enterprise is an aggregate of various resources, mainly including the following three aspects: The source of the enterprise's competitive advantage is the special heterogeneous resources Valuable & Rare, the sustainability of competitive advantage is the imitable resources Inimitable, and the acquisition and management of special resources Organizable. However, the theory focuses more on the importance of internal resources of the enterprise. When the external environment of the enterprise changes, the strategy generated at this time may not be applicable to the development requirements of the market.

International Investment Research

International investment refers to the economic behavior that official institutions, multinational corporations, financial institutions, and individuals, including residents, flow their monetary or industrial capital to form physical assets, intangible assets, or financial assets, and realize value appreciation through transnational operation. According to the above definition, we can conclude that the subjects of international investment are economic legal persons and natural persons who have independent investment decision-making power and are responsible for the investment results. The object of international investment behavior is the object that the investment subject finally realizes the investment goal by means of operation, including but not only including physical assets, intangible assets and financial assets. The fundamental purpose of international investment is to realize the increment of capital. As a kind of expanding economic behavior, international investment inevitably involves two countries, namely the investing country and the host country. The investing country can also be called capital outflow country or foreign investment country, which refers to the country where the economic subject engaged in foreign investment activities is located. Host country can also be called capital inflow country or capital recipient country, mainly refers to the country that allows and absorbs foreign capital to invest in its own country and receives foreign capital loans. International investment is generally divided into two forms. One is to invest abroad. For the investing country, especially for the developed country, it is an important way to find a way out for the excess capital and seek high profits overseas. For the host country, especially for the developing countries, this is one of the important channels to attract and utilize foreign capital to solve the domestic shortage of funds and introduce foreign advanced technology and management knowledge to promote the development of the country's economy. In the case of a country, participation in international investment activities can occur in two different provinces, the investing country or the host country. When it appears as an investment country, its economic behavior is manifested as foreign investment; when it appears as a host country, its economic behavior is manifested as the introduction of foreign investment.

The relationship between strategic environment and the choice of enterprise development The strategy is assumed

The strategic environment of an enterprise has always been an important factor affecting the decision-making of enterprise leaders. Chandler (1962) pointed out the interaction between environment, strategy and organizational structure, and believed that corporate strategy should adapt to environmental changes to meet market needs, while organizational structure must adapt to corporate strategy requirements. Ansoff (1965) believed that the strategic starting point of an enterprise is the pursuit of its own survival and development, and strategic behavior is the process of adapting to its environment and the resulting internal structural process of the enterprise. Zhao Xibin (2004) believes that "the internal environment and external environment of an enterprise, the components of the enterprise environment, and the enterprise and the environment are dynamic and interactive relations that are interdependent and influence each other." Thus, it can be seen that there is a complex cooperative evolution relationship between enterprise strategy and environment. Based on the theory of strategic choice, we know that enterprise strategic environment can positively influence enterprise strategic choice. Child (1972) proposed that enterprises do not always passively adapt to the environment, and organizations also have the opportunity and ability to reshape the environment to meet their own goals. The theory holds that organizational strategy has great influence on organizational environment. Enterprises can consider adopting a variety of strategies to seek the most powerful development space for the organization through the interaction with the external environment. Child also points out that contingency theory ignores that organizations have the right to choose who changes or controls the organization. Porter (1985) pointed out that the increase or decrease of industrial attraction of competitive strategy was quite influential. At the same time, enterprises can significantly enhance or weaken their competitive position in the industry through strategic choice. Therefore, competitive strategy not only responds to the environment, but also tries to shape the environment according to the profits of the firm. It can be seen that enterprise strategy has a transformative effect on enterprise environment.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Definition: Research design is the execution plan of the whole research process. In general, research design has three basic purposes: (1) to effectively answer research questions; (2) Meet the requirements of empirical research validity; (3) Control various variables involved in the study. According to this study of the internalization of enterprise strategic management, the core value and related theory, discuss the current economic situation, the influencing factors of development strategy of auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu province and its influence degree, respectively constructed cooperative development strategy mode and forward-looking development strategy mode, the development of auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu province strategic factors of the influence factors of the enterprise performance model. Taking the strategic development of auto parts enterprises in Jiangsu province as the research object, the influencing factor models of enterprise development strategy selection are established from five aspects such as policy environment, and the relationship between different enterprise development strategy models and enterprise performance is deeply analyzed.

Population/ Sample /Unit of Analysis

By 2019, there are 643 autonomous auto parts enterprises above scale (annual output value ≥ 0.2 billion YUAN) in Jiangsu Province, with industrial output value exceeding 100 billion yuan. A total of 1286 invention patents have been completed, accounting for 90.6%; a total of 17 provincial-level enterprise technology centers have been built, forming a mature auto parts industry development pattern that combines technology research and development with intelligent manufacturing.

According to the above development status, based on the research hypothesis, the relevant professionals in Jiangsu auto parts manufacturing enterprises were investigated, 22 test variables and 38 measurement questions were formed, and the first draft of the questionnaire was designed. In order to find out the commonness and difference of the factors influencing the development strategy formulation of auto parts manufacturing enterprises in Jiangsu province, the online questionnaire covers 32 cities (counties), such as Nanjing, Changzhou, Suzhou and Wuxi. Field questionnaires were mainly distributed in Changzhou, Wuxi, Suzhou and other places. Random sampling method was adopted and only distributed to professionals in the auto parts manufacturing industry to ensure the validity of the questionnaire. The total number of samples obtained in this study was 495.

Validity and Reliability Test

The reliability and validity test of questionnaire is a necessary guarantee to ensure the validity of follow-up analysis. Reliability and validity tests of questionnaires are carried out for scales. Reliability test is usually adopted in SPSS reliability test, while exploratory factor analysis or confirmatory factor analysis is adopted in validity analysis.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability refers to the Stability and Consistency of the results measured by a test or scale tool. The greater the Reliability of the scale, the smaller the standard error of measurement. Reliability analysis is a method to estimate the Consistency of the measurement results. In classical measurement theory, reliability is the ratio of the variance of the true fraction to the variance of the actual fraction. Simply put, reliability refers to reliability, consistency, or stability. For example, if you measure the same object and the results are very close to each other multiple times, you will think that the results are reliable, true, and high reliability. If the results of each measurement are significantly different, it indicates low reliability. Similarly, in the questionnaire research, reliability analysis is also used to measure the authenticity and reliability of sample answers. The higher the reliability of the test, the more reliable the results are. Reliability can be further divided into internal reliability and external reliability. Therefore, reliability can be divided into internal reliability and external reliability. Intrinsic reliability: it refers to measuring whether multiple questions in the research questionnaire measure the same concept or content, that is, whether there is internal consistency among questions. This is the reliability analysis that most questionnaires do. External reliability: usually refers to whether the measurement results are consistent at different times.

Validity Analysis

Validity refers to the degree to which psychological or behavioral traits designed by the test can be measured. Validity analysis is simply the validity and accuracy of questionnaire

design. When we design the questionnaire for the research topic, we always hope that the question actually measures what we want to measure, so that the research data can accurately explain the problem. Validity can be divided into content validity, structure validity and criterion validity. Content validity refers to the reasonableness of the questionnaire items on the measurement of related concepts, which is usually illustrated by words. For example, use references or authoritative sources to explain the authority and validity of the questionnaire. In addition, the validity of the questionnaire is fully explained through the pre-test of the questionnaire and the correction of the item based on the results. Structural validity refers to the corresponding relationship between measurement items and measurement dimensions. There are two measurement methods, one is exploratory factor analysis, the other is confirmatory factor analysis. Exploratory factor analysis is the most widely used method of structure validity measurement. When using exploratory factor analysis for validity verification, variables or scales should be analyzed separately based on scales. In addition, there is also valid criterion validity. If there was an authoritative and standard scale data before, the scale is still used for research and a data is collected. The previous authoritative standard data is used as the standard, and correlation analysis is conducted between the current data and the previous data. If the correlation value is high, it indicates that the criterion validity is good.

Data Collection Process

Data Collection

First of all, in the process of data collection of empirical research, aiming at the development status of jiangsu automobile enterprises, a variety of data collection methods are selected in the data collection. The main data collection methods are questionnaire survey, expert interview and financial data collection.

(1) Questionnaire method: This study makes an in-depth analysis of the current development status of jiangsu automobile industry, and reasonably designs relevant questionnaires according to the relevant questions in this study. The questionnaires are distributed in online and offline forms, and the relevant questionnaires are collected and analyzed.

(2) Expert interview method: In the process of expert interview, data were collected from two aspects. First of all, for the index data of jiangsu auto parts enterprises involved in this study, experts were interviewed by relevant researchers of auto enterprises, the rationality of the questionnaire was analyzed, and the reliability and validity of the questionnaire were further tested. Secondly, according to the research direction, the content of structured interview is designed, and the views on the development status and development direction of jiangsu component enterprises are obtained from the perspective of relevant experts.

(3) Financial data collection: According to the classification standard whether to be listed or not, the financial and operating conditions of the enterprises involved in this study were collected, and the data content was processed and processed. The enterprises with missing data were removed. Finally, the relevant financial data of jiangsu auto parts enterprises were obtained.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

Profile of Respondents

In the process of data collection, this study mainly takes the automobile manufacturing industry in Jiangsu Province as the research object. According to the above development status, based on the research hypothesis, the relevant professionals in Jiangsu auto parts manufacturing enterprises were investigated, and 29 measurement questions with 12 variables were formed, and the preliminary questionnaire was designed. In order to find out the commonness and difference of the factors influencing the development strategy formulation of auto parts manufacturing enterprises in Jiangsu province, the online questionnaire covers 32 cities (counties), such as Nanjing, Changzhou, Suzhou and Wuxi. In the process of conducting the questionnaire survey, the enterprises surveyed covered all links of the production chain of auto parts industry, and distributed to Changzhou, Wuxi and Suzhou, the auto parts industry clusters in Jiangsu Province. To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, random sampling method was used to distribute the questionnaire only to professionals in the auto parts manufacturing industry. Based on the above research assumptions, this paper used online and offline methods to issue questionnaires and collect data. According to the research results of relevant literature, sample size will have a certain impact on the research results. Therefore, in the formal survey, 530 questionnaires were issued in this study, of which 495 were effective, with an effective rate of 93.3%. The specific sample overview is shown in Table 4-1 below.

Table 4-1 Survey sample profile

Disbursement	Released quantity	Recycling quantity	Recovery	Effective number	Effective rate
Field visit	100	100	100%	100	100%
intermediary agent	300	297	99.0%	291	97%
network	130	122	93.8%	104	80%
A combined	530	519	97.9%	495	93.3%

Enterprise Nature

As an important base of China's auto industry, Jiangsu province has 643 independent auto parts enterprises. According to the results of the questionnaire, a total of 40 manufacturing enterprises are involved in this paper. According to the nature of enterprises, there are 6 state-owned enterprises, 19 state-owned holding enterprises, 1 foreign-funded enterprise, 3 joint ventures and 11 private enterprises. Figure 4-1 shows the proportion of enterprises by type.

Research Objective 1 (R.O.1) Political Environment and Enterprise Development Strategy

In this paper, descriptive statistical analysis, Cronbach α coefficient analysis and factor analysis were carried out on 495 valid questionnaires. The reliability and validity of the scale were confirmed. Then, correlation analysis and regression analysis are carried out on the statistical

data according to the measured variables. Finally, structural model testing is carried out on the basis of regression analysis to determine whether the hypothesis is valid or not.

1. Correlation analysis: In this paper, auto parts manufacturers in Jiangsu Province are taken as the research object. The investigated data contain many interrelated variables. Therefore, correlation analysis must be carried out before multiple regression and structural model testing to determine the degree of correlation between each variable. At the same time, the results of correlation analysis meet the requirements of relevance, which is the basis of hypothesis testing. In the analysis of the role of strategic environment and enterprise development strategy, this paper takes political environment as the basis to test the relevance of items contained in variables such as cultural environment, financing policy, service policy and access policy. The results show that there is a good correlation between the measurement items of test variables in the political environment, as shown in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Correlation analysis of measurement items

	A11	A12	A21	A31	A41	A42
A11	1					
A12	0.38 **	1				
A21	0.42 **	0.28 **	1			
A31	0.28 **	0.25 **	0.29 **	1		
A41	0.40 **	0.13 **	0.14 **	0.03 **	1	
A42	0.31 **	0.21 **	0.22 **	0.27 **	0.23 **	1

Note: ***P<0.001, **P<0.01, *P<0.05

2. Regression analysis: Regression analysis is the basis of structural equation model. This paper uses SPSS19.0 system software to verify the effect of political environment on enterprise development strategy of auto parts manufacturing enterprises in Jiangsu Province. It is worth noting that the variables in this regression analysis belong to unidimensional variables. According to the theoretical principle of regression analysis, when the measurement scale has good consistency, it can be represented by the average value of the measurement variables. Therefore, this paper uses the average value of the items contained in each measurement variable to represent it. According to the hypothesis, performance and the independent variable on the dependent variable in this paper insert intervening variable between political environment enterprise strategic mode, enterprise political environment including cultural environment, financing policy, service, access policy such as the independent variable, adopt the way of all sample data regression analysis, the regression analysis results as shown in table 4-4.

Table 4-4 Regression analysis of the influence of political environment on enterprise strategy

Measured variables	The coefficient of β	T value	Significant	F value	VIF value
Cultural Environment (A1)	537.	8.709***	000.		1.023
Financing Policy (A2)	012.	158.	017.	19.817***	1.045
Service Policy (A3)	177.	1.014.	024.		1.019
Access Policy (A4)	018.	070.	021.		1.057

Note: P < 0.05

According to the regression analysis of the influence of political environment on enterprise strategy in Table 4-4, it can be seen that the goodness of fit F value of the regression model is (19.817***), indicating that it has good significance. In addition, the VIF value of the collinearity

test results is close to 1, which meets the regression requirements. At the same time, the significance level of T value of regression test results all fell within the range of (0.00-0.05), indicating a good significance level. The β coefficients of regression detection structures are all greater than 0, indicating that there is an obvious positive effect. The regression analysis and structural model analysis results of the influence of political environment on the development strategy of the secondary component manufacturing enterprises in Jiangsu province show that the political environment has a significant positive effect on the development strategy of enterprises, and the analysis results have obvious verification of hypothesis H1 and H2, indicating that the hypothesis is valid, as shown in Table 4-6.

Table 4-6 Hypothetical results of the influence of policy environment on enterprise development strategy

Serial number	Hypothetical content	Whether it's set up
Hypothesis H1	Policy influences the choice of cooperative development strategy has positive correlation	Set up
Hypothesis H2	There is a positive correlation between policy influence and prospective development strategy choice	Set up

Discussion

Political environment is the external environment of enterprise strategy, and it is also the first factor that enterprises should consider when making strategy, which plays an obvious role in regulating the system of enterprise strategy. To put it simply, political environment refers to the external political form of enterprise operation and management activities, which has typical integrity and comprehensiveness and affects the survival and development of enterprises from the macro dimension. Therefore, the policy environment is closely related to the strategic development of Jiangsu auto parts manufacturing enterprises and other manufacturing enterprises in the industry. For example, before China's reform and opening up, the planned economy system was implemented. This political environment greatly restricted the development of private enterprises, and it was difficult for state-owned enterprises to achieve great development under this "nanny" system. However, since the reform and opening up, in order to promote the rapid development of the market economy, the state has issued a series of policies and guidelines conducive to the development of enterprises, improve the market competition environment, greatly stimulate the development of private enterprises, for the contemporary hundred birds, a hundred flowers bloom enterprise development environment has laid a foundation.

Research Objective 2 (R.O.2) Enterprise Strategic Capability and Enterprise Development Strategy

According to the article content measurement scale, the ability of enterprise strategic impact on enterprise development strategy research, measuring variables respectively, entrepreneurial ability, knowledge, ability, ability three aspects such as layout, entrepreneurs' ability to include five test items, knowledge ability includes two test items, layout ability includes two test items. The mediating variable strategy model includes forward-looking development strategy and cooperative development strategy. According to the logic of mathematical statistics, the row correlation analysis and regression analysis of variables are

firstly measured, and then the structural model is tested based on regression analysis to determine whether the hypothesis is valid or not.

1. Correlation analysis: In the analysis of the influence of enterprise strategic ability and enterprise development strategy, this paper takes enterprise strategic ability as the basis to test the correlation of items contained in variables such as entrepreneurial ability, knowledge ability and layout ability. The results show that there is a good correlation between the measurement items of the test variables of enterprise strategic ability, as shown in Table 4-7 and subsequent Table 4-7.

Table 4-7 Correlation analysis of measurement items

	B11	B12	B13	B14	B15	B21
B11	1					
B12	0.21 **	1				
B13	0.32 **	0.22 **	1			
B14	0.27 **	0.35 **	0.27 **	1		
B15	0.35 **	0.04 **	0.24 **	0.03 **	1	
B21	0.26 **	0.21 **	0.12 **	0.24 **	0.28 **	1
B22	0.41 **	0.45 **	0.07 **	0.14 **	0.06 **	0.34 **
B31	0.33 **	0.37 **	0.35 **	0.24 **	0.08 **	0.25 **
B32	0.45 **	0.19 **	0.26 **	0.42 **	0.14 **	0.18 **

Note: ***P<0.001, **P<0.01, *P<0.05

Table 4-7 Correlation analysis of measurement items

	B22	B31	B32
B22	1		
B31	0.39 **	1	
B32	0.44 **	0.31 **	1

Note: ***P<0.001, **P<0.01, *P<0.05

2. Regression analysis: This paper uses SPSS19.0 system software to verify the function of strategic capability of jiangsu auto parts manufacturing enterprises on enterprise development strategy. The variables in the regression analysis are unidimensional variables. According to the theoretical principle of regression analysis, when the measurement scale has good consistency, the mean value of the measurement variables can be represented. Therefore, this paper uses the average value of the items contained in each measurement variable to represent it. According to the hypothesis, performance and the independent variable on the dependent variable in this paper insert intervening variable between political environment enterprise strategic mode, enterprise strategic ability to ability to entrepreneurs, intellectual ability, layout for measuring variables, there are 9 test, with the method of all sample data regression analysis, the regression analysis results as shown in table 4 to 8.

CONCLUSION

Enterprise development strategy plays a "compass" role for auto parts manufacturing enterprises and plays a pivotal role in the development of enterprises. Therefore, studying enterprise development strategy and exploring the factors affecting it can bring guidance and inspiration to enterprise managers.

Theoretical enlightenment: As a typical manufacturing enterprise, the strategic factors of jiangsu auto parts manufacturing enterprises, such as strategic environment, strategic ability,

technological innovation ability, interest correlation and market competition degree, all affect the strategic formulation of enterprises, and have positive and negative effects on enterprise performance. Among them, strategic environment refers to the external policy environment of the enterprise, including cultural policy, financing policy, service policy, introduction policy and other four aspects, and all have an impact on the choice of enterprise strategic mode; Technological strategic ability is the ability of enterprise strategy formulation and implementation, including entrepreneurial ability, knowledge ability, layout ability; Technological creativity is the ability of enterprises to occupy market competitive advantages, and it is also the ability of enterprises to remove technological obstacles in the process of strategic implementation. This paper investigates from four dimensions: r&d expenditure investment, independent intellectual property rights, proportion of technical personnel, and r&d organizational ability. In addition, there are interest correlation, market competition degree and so on, the empirical study of the influence of these factors on enterprise strategy, not only enriches the connotation of manufacturing enterprise strategy, but also provides a theoretical reference for enterprises to take correct strategic measures. At the same time, China's current research on the strategy of auto parts enterprises is obviously insufficient, lack of systematic and integrity, a small part of the research is still through qualitative analysis, lack of theoretical demonstration. This paper focuses on practical research, and through empirical analysis can help enterprises more clearly understand and grasp the strategic formulation and implementation of auto parts manufacturing enterprises, and improve the strategic development ability of enterprises. Moreover, among the influencing factors of enterprise development strategy, the strategic mode changes according to the size and development direction of the enterprise, which can be divided into forward-looking strategy and cooperative strategy. Different factors have positive and negative influences on different strategic modes.

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